

COMPUTATIONAL MODEL FOR STRUCTURE DETERMINATION OF THE
 $\text{Na}_4\text{Ag}_{44}(\text{P-MBA})_{30}$ NANOPARTICLE SUPERSTRUCTURE

by

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Abstract

$\text{Na}_4\text{Ag}_{44}(\text{p-MBA})_{30}$ is a nanoparticle that can form a crystal lattice.¹ The structure of this crystal has been previously studied with the Le Bail method.¹ However, structural information obtained with this method is limited since it only provides information about the symmetry and the unit cell parameters, but not on atomic positions. The Rietveld method can find the atomic positions of the crystal structure. However, this method requires an initial guess and for this system, that is a difficult task given the number of atoms present in the nanoparticle. Simulated annealing is able to provide an initial guess, and rigid bodies reduces the number of variables. The goal of this project was to use Rietveld refinements, simulated annealing, and rigid bodies to determine the structure of the material as it is subjected to increasing pressures. Diffraction patterns of the crystal at different pressures were plotted in a colormap. The analysis of the patterns showed that there is insufficient data to perform a Rietveld refinement with simulated annealing and rigid bodies.

1 Introduction

The $\text{Na}_4\text{Ag}_{44}(\text{p-MBA})_{30}$ nanoparticle superstructure is nanoparticle that has been previously synthesized.¹ The nanoparticles consist of an inorganic core containing 44 silver atoms that is surrounded by a shell of *p*-mercaptobenzoic acid(*p*-MBA) organic ligands.¹ Neighboring nanoparticles interact with each other through hydrogen bonding forming a crystal lattice. This material has potential use for sensing, catalysis, and medicine.² The material has been subjected to a range of high pressures, and structural information was obtained in the form of x-ray diffraction from synchrotron source under those conditions. Unit cell parameters and symmetry have been studied with the Le Bail method.¹ Structural information on the atomic positions of the atoms in the unit cell is lacking requiring further analysis of the data. This investigation presents an analysis of the diffraction data at increasing pressure of $\text{Na}_4\text{Ag}_{44}(\text{p-MBA})_{30}$ to determine its crystal structure with the Rietveld method, simulated annealing, and rigid bodies.

1.1 Structure of a Crystal

A crystal is a type of solid that is defined by a repeating arrangement of atoms in three dimensions. The structure of a crystal is composed of the unit cell parameters, and the atomic positions which are related to one another through symmetry. The unit cell is the section that contains the simplest arrangement of atoms that repeats in all directions within the crystal. This unit cell is defined by the cell parameters which are the lengths of three of the edges of the cell and the three angles between each pair of edges. In a crystal, the lengths are designated as a , b , and c ; while the angles are α , β , and γ .^{3,4} **Figure 1** shows a unit cell along its parameter, edge distances and angles.

Figure 1. Image of a generic unit cell with its lattice parameters.

The possible symmetries for unit cell parameters depend on the ability of the unit cell to cover all space in such a way that the environment in all unit cells is the same. The parameters that satisfy these conditions result in seven different crystal systems: cubic, tetragonal, orthorhombic, monoclinic, hexagonal, rhombohedral, and triclinic.^{3,4} However, the atoms in each system can result in multiple arrangements that satisfy the same a , b , and c lengths as well as the same α , β , and γ angles. Bravais Lattices are the possible arrangements of atoms in a unit cell that result in the repeating arrangement of atoms through the crystal. There exists 14 of these Bravais Lattices. Additionally, symmetry can characterize the structure of the crystal.^{3,4} The symmetry operations that achieve this are translation, reflection in a point, reflection in a plane, rotation about an axis, and rotation followed by reflection in a point. All the possible combination of operations that can be performed are referred as crystal classes and amount to 32 total classes.^{3,4}

Solving the crystal structure requires knowledge of the atomic positions. This knowledge can be obtained with the use diffraction techniques. In these methods, either x-rays or neutrons are irradiated a crystal sample. The repeating nature of the crystals means that parallel planes of atoms exist throughout the crystal. The x-rays emitted by a source reach the atoms in the solid and are scattered in an elastic process. For given angles, the light scattered by parallel planes constructively interferes, and this produces a signal that can be measured by the instrument.⁴ **Figure 2** shows the crystal lattice of sodium chloride (a), the angles and distances within the crystal (b), and two sets of planes of atoms in a crystal (c, d).⁵

Figure 2. Image of the lattice of the sodium chloride crystal (a), angles and distances present in the lattice (b), and two sets of planes involved in refraction (c, d).⁵

Bragg's law describes the relationship between the angle of incidence and the interplanar distance. This law is represented by the following equation:

$$\lambda = 2d\sin\theta \tag{1}$$

Where λ is the wavelength of x-rays, d is the distance between the planes, and θ is the angle of incidence. The distance between the planes reveals information about the crystal structure. This is achieved by plotting the intensity of the signal against an angle axis 2θ as a diffraction pattern.^{3,4}

1.2 Structure Determination Methods

The diffraction pattern is used to determine the structure of the crystal by various computational methods such as the Le Bail method and the Rietveld refinement. In these methods, various variables are used to calculate a diffraction pattern based on the model structure. This pattern is then compared with the experimental pattern with the objective of finding a calculated pattern that most resembles the experimental pattern given specific fitting metrics explained below. **Figure 3** shows the relationship between the different methods available to determine the structure of a crystal. It also shows what each method is able to achieve and its requirements.^{3,4,6}

Figure 3. Relationship between the different structure determination method, their results, and their requirements.

1.2.1 Le Bail Method

The Le Bail method is used to obtain integrated intensities of diffraction patterns. This method allows the determination of the unit cell parameters and the symmetry of the crystal. In the Le Bail method, it is assumed that the integrated intensities are the same.^{3,4} The intensities are calculated from starting parameters and the least-squares method is applied to determine the difference between the calculated intensities and observed intensities.³ The method follows a similar process as the Rietveld refinement as the least-squares method is applied to the fitting. The integrated intensities from the first run are used as the intensities for the new run in an iterative process. The process is repeated until the integrated intensities converge.³ The Le Bail method allows for the determination of the unit cell size and the symmetry before performing a Rietveld refinement.

1.2.2 Rietveld Refinement

In a Rietveld refinement, a least squares method is used to determine the structure of the crystal from an initial model. The goal of the least-squares minimization is to obtain the best fit between the calculated pattern from the proposed structure and the experimental pattern. The unit cell parameters, atomic positions, thermal parameters, and occupancies are considered in the minimization. In the refinement, the parameters of the proposed structure are varied and the intensities corresponding to those parameters are calculated.

The best fit between the two patterns is assessed by comparing the difference between the observed intensities and the calculated intensities. The *R*-factor is used to assess this difference. This value is calculated from the difference between the observed intensity and the calculated intensity and is calculated with the equation:

$$R_f = \frac{\sum_j |\sqrt{I_{obs,j}} - \sqrt{I_{calc,j}}|}{\sum_j \sqrt{I_{obs,j}}} \quad (2)$$

Where R_f is the criteria used to assess the difference. The pattern consists of a series of steps (j) throughout the range of angles measured, and each step is associated with an intensity. The I_{obs} and the I_{calc} are the intensities values at each j step.³ A perfect fit would yield an R value of zero.

If the R_f value is small enough, the refinement is accepted, and the model used for the initial calculations is used as a representation of the crystal.³ However, this model may not represent the correct structure of the crystal. An initial model of a structure is required to obtain the parameters to calculate the intensities that are refined. Therefore, the Rietveld refinement requires that the initial model is close to the correct structure of the crystal to ensure that the minimization yields an accurate structure. This requirement raises because the system possibly contains multiple local energy minima. An erroneous initial structure could be refined towards a local minimum that is far from the correct structure.³

1.2.3 Simulated Annealing

The Rietveld method requires proposing a structure for the refinement process. For simple systems, the possible structure can be obtained by inspecting the chemical composition of the system. Proposing a structure can be easily achieved if the unit cell contains a small number of atoms. The process become more difficult with crystals that contain a large number of motifs.

Additionally, the proposed structure of the crystal must be close to actual structure of the crystal. The Rietveld method consists in decreasing the difference between the simulated and the experimental patterns. The parameters are changed to decrease the difference.³ The refinement can result in a crystal structure at a local minimum if the proposed structure varies greatly from the structure at the global minimum. A local minimum that is far from the global minimum results in an inaccurate representation of the crystal structure.³

Simulated annealing is a method that eliminates the necessity of proposing an initial structure in the Rietveld refinement. In this method, an algorithm creates a random structural model.^{3,4} The parameters are randomly changed, which can result in better or worst fits.^{3,4} These changes allow the structural model to escape from local minima and approach the global minimum.⁶⁻¹⁰ **Figure 4** shows an illustration of the process of simulated annealing. The initial structure is close to a local minimum which could lead to inaccurate structure with the use of the Rietveld method. With the simulated annealing, the model can move out of the global minimum as represented with the blue arrows. This change eventually leads to the global minimum.

Figure 4. Illustration of the simulated annealing process. The y-axis is the goodness of fit parameter, and the x-axis represents the possible structures.

1.2.4 Rigid Bodies

The rigid bodies procedure allows the simplification of the system to be studied with a Rietveld refinement. This strategy consists in setting restrictions on the bond lengths and the angles between atoms.^{3,4} These values are allowed minimum change through the process of the refinement. A molecule that is subjected to this method behaves a single unit that undergoes rotation and translation in space as the refinement progresses.

By considering the molecule as a single object, the number of variables is reduced.³ Additionally, the integrity of the molecule is preserved.^{3,4} This integrity is important because it is possible for the refinement to break bonds that would not be broken in the actual crystal. The refinement could move bonded atoms to a distance that would be equivalent to breaking the bond.

1.3 Silver Nanoparticle Superlattice

The $\text{Na}_4\text{Ag}_{44}(\text{p-MBA})_{30}$ nanoparticle superstructure contains a core composed of 44 silver atoms that is bonded to 30 p-MBA ligands.¹ The carboxyl groups at the ends of ligands of neighboring nanoparticles create hydrogen bonding.^{1,9} As a result of these interactions, the nanoparticles form a solid with long range crystal ordering. **Figure 5** shows the structure of the p-mercaptobenzoic acid (p-MBA).

Figure 5. Structure of p-Mercaptobenzoic acid.

The material's unit cell parameters and symmetry has been studied with the Le Bail method.¹ The reported unit cell parameters are $a = 26.018 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 26.018 \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 51.551 \text{ \AA}$; and unit cell angles are $\alpha = 59.688^\circ$, $\beta = 90^\circ$ and $\gamma = 120^\circ$.^{1,9} The structural information was obtained from single-crystal X-ray diffraction from a synchrotron source. **Figure 6** presents the structure of a single nanoparticle along with an image of the previously proposed triclinic crystal lattice. The hydrogen bonding that allows the interactions between adjacent nanoparticles is also shown.

Figure 6. Image of a single $\text{Na}_4\text{Ag}_{44}(\text{p-MBA})_{30}$ nanoparticle (a), representation of the interaction between two nanoparticles through hydrogen bonding between adjacent carboxylic acid groups (b), and preliminary unit cell of the crystal (c).^{1,11}

Computational models predicted gear-like rotation when pressure is applied to the crystal as shown in **Figure 7**.^{1,3,10} The Le Bail method has been used to obtain the unit cell parameters at pressures up to 8.12 GPa.

Figure 7. Nanoparticles at low pressure (left) and nanoparticles forming gear-like structure at high pressure (left).^{1,11}

However, the large number of atoms and the interactions between silver nanoparticles and organic ligands results in a complex system in containing several dozen atoms. Simulated annealing has been used to perform Rietveld refinements to determine the position of organic molecules present within the channels of the silicalite framework and of metallic-organic frameworks.^{11,14} Similarly, simulated annealing was used to determine the position of organic compounds in the Germanate framework.¹² It has also been used for structure determination of crystals containing Zr, Hf, P, and O atoms.¹³

The $\text{Na}_4\text{Ag}_{44}(\text{p-MBA})_{30}$ system contains a large number of atoms making the process of proposing a model for the simplest unit cell challenging. Additionally, pressure is another variable that must be considered since it changes can change the structure of the crystal as predicted by the computational analysis. With the use of simulated annealing, a model of the $\text{Na}_4\text{Ag}_{44}(\text{p-MBA})$ system can be proposed to avoid the difficulty in creating an initial guess.

The presence of organic ligands adds variables to the system due to the presence of a large number of atoms. Additionally, organic ligands contain bonds that are stable and unlikely to break. The ligand in the nanoparticle, p-MBA, contains a benzene ring, which is very stable due to its conjugate π -system. Performing a Rietveld refinement has the potential effect of breaking the bonds in the ligands. The rigid bodies method can be used to perform a refinement on materials containing organic molecules. With this technique, molecules can be refined as a unit that can move and can rotate.^{6,7}

2 Methods

The data was analyzed with the MATLAB software. Dr. Terry Bigioni provided 133 data files of diffraction patterns taken at the pressure range from uncompressed to 8.12 GPa. The large number of files makes the process of performing the Rietveld refinements long and inefficient. From an inspection of the data, the diffraction patterns of consecutive pressure steps showed little change in terms of peak position and intensity. This little change means that the structure is very similar

or identical within close pressure steps. Plotting all the files into a colormap can reveal the patterns that show significant differences between each other and that could be used for the Rietveld refinement. This condensation of the data reduces the amount of time to determine the structure since simulated annealing, rigid bodies, and Rietveld refinement would have to be performed only for the patterns that contain unique structural information. In contrast, it would be required to apply the three methods to all 133 data files.

The files were uploaded to the MATLAB coding environment. The data in each of the files was turned into matrices which is necessary to perform any operation on MATLAB. These matrices were then used to generate a 3D plot of the diffraction data. To obtain a clear image of the changes in the peak positions, the intensity was expressed with a color dimension. The x-axis represents the degrees and the y-axis the pressure. By looking at the xy plane of the 3D map, the changes of peak positions with increasing pressure could be observed. This colormap then provided with the pressure steps that can show unique structural information.

3 Results and Discussion

The diffraction patterns show a small number of peaks. **Figure 8** presents one of the diffraction patterns analyzed. Two large peaks are present at around 2° . Between 3° and 4° , there are two smaller peaks followed by a slightly smaller peak at $\sim 4.5^\circ$. For angles larger than 5° the peak intensities are consistently small.

Figure 8. X-ray diffraction pattern of uncompressed crystal. The most prominent peaks are found on the 2θ angle range from 1° to 14° .

The colormap shown in **Figure 9** shows the intensities of the peaks as a color based on the scale on the right. The y-axis in this figure represents the pressure steps of the corresponding diffraction patterns. The two peaks near 2° from **Figure 8** show little change in position with only a slight turn to the right at around step 60 that later turn to smaller angles. However, the right peak splits at around the 30th step and follows the trend as the original peak. Both of these peaks show a decrease in intensity as show by the change in color. The two peaks between 3° and 4° similarly show little change in position when increasing pressure.

Peaks above 5° become difficult to see because their intensity is significantly small compared with the more intense peak closer to 2° . Nonetheless, these peaks tend to increase in angle with increasing pressure.

Figure 9. Colormap of the diffraction patterns for increasing pressure. The x-axis shows the angle 2θ of the diffraction. The y-axis presents the pressure steps with higher number representing higher pressure patterns. The peak intensity is given by the color bar in which red represents higher intensities and the blue the lower intensities.

Overall, there are about five major peaks in the range of 2° to 5° with several smaller peaks above that range. From **Figure 9**, we see that there are approximately 12 small peaks. The number of peaks seen in **Figure 8** does not change as the pressure is increase which can be observed in **Figure 9**. This small number of peaks means there is little data about the crystal present on the pattern. The number of reflections represented by the patterns is then approximately 12.

There is a large number of variables present in each of the nanoparticles present in the crystal. A single nanoparticle contains 44 Ag atoms and 30 organic ligands. Each of the ligands is made from a benzene ring, a carboxyl group, and a sulfur atom. Given the number of ligands in the

nanoparticle, there are several dozen atoms involved in bonding. Rigid bodies reduced the number of atomic variables to 30 variables in terms of ligands.

The simplest possible crystal lattice contains one nanoparticle. Based on the number of silver atoms and ligands, there are 74 motifs. Each of these motifs accounts for three variables of movement in space which means that there are more than 200 variables in the system. Additionally, the ligands contain an axis of rotation which adds more variables to the system. Pressure is another variable present because the system is being compressed. Overall, the simplest lattice, which contains a single nanoparticle, contain several hundred variables.

The large number of atoms and organic ligands makes the refinement of the crystal complex. The number of variables present in the simplest case is large while the amount of data present in the diffraction patterns is small. The variables outnumber the data available. When considering systems with more nanoparticles present, the difference means that the patterns cannot account for all of the variables.³ In consequence, performing a Rietveld refinement on this system cannot yield an accurate representation of the crystal. Therefore, the data available is insufficient to perform a Rietveld refinement with simulated annealing and rigid bodies.

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